

1 **Desorption Isotherms and Net Isotheric Heat of Chestnut Flour** 2 **and Starch**

3 **Francisco Chenlo · Ramón Moreira · Diego M. Prieto · María D. Torres**

4
5 **Abstract** The desorption isotherms of chestnut flour and chestnut starch were
6 determined at different temperatures (20, 35, 50 and 65 °C) using gravimetric
7 method. Desorption isotherms of potato starch were also determined in order to
8 establish a comparison against desorption isotherms of chestnut starch. Several
9 saturated salt solutions were selected to generate different water activities in the
10 range of 0.09 to 0.91. Obtained desorption isotherms were of type II, according to
11 Brunauer's classification. Modified BET and GAB models satisfactorily fitted the
12 experimental data for all systems studies, although the last one can be considered
13 better based on obtained statistical parameters and because it is applicable in a
14 broader water activity range. The average monolayer moisture content (kg (kg
15 d.b.)⁻¹) calculated by GAB model was 0.059 ± 0.007 for chestnut flour, $0.103 \pm$
16 0.021 for chestnut starch and 0.060 ± 0.028 for potato starch. The net isosteric
17 sorption heat, calculated by means of Clausius-Clapeyron equation, decreased
18 when moisture content increased. The maximum values of net isosteric sorption
19 heat (kJ mol⁻¹) were approximately 27.5 for chestnut flour, 16.0 for chestnut
20 starch and 33.0 for potato starch at in the range of temperature from 20 to 50 °C.

21 **Running title:** Desorption Isotherms of Chestnut Flour and Starch

22 **Keywords:** Water activity; Moisture content; Starch; Chestnut; Sorption heat.

1

Francisco Chenlo · Ramón Moreira (✉) · Diego M. Prieto · María D. Torres

Departamento de Enxeñaría Química, Universidade de Santiago de Compostela,

Rúa Lope Gómez de Marzoa s/n, Santiago de Compostela 15782, Spain,

e-mail: ramon.moreira@usc.es

23 **Nomenclature**

24	a_w	Water activity
25	C	GAB (Eq. 1) parameter
26	C_B	BET (Eq. 1) parameter
27	E	Mean relative percentage deviation modulus
28	E_{RMS}	Root mean square error (kg (kg d.b.) ⁻¹)
29	H	Heat of GAB model (kJ mol ⁻¹)
30	h	Sorption heat (kJ mol ⁻¹)
31	h_L	Heat of water condensation (kJ mol ⁻¹)
32	K	GAB (Eq. 1) parameter
33	n	Number of samples
34	N	BET (Eq. 1) parameter
35	R	Ideal gas constant (8.314 J (mol K) ⁻¹)
36	R^2	Coefficient of determination
37	T	Absolute temperature (K)
38	X	Equilibrium moisture content (kg (kg d.b.) ⁻¹)

39

40 **Subscript**

41	cal	Calculated
42	e	Net isosteric
43	exp	Experimental
44	M	Monolayer of GAB model
45	MB	Monolayer of BET model
46	N	Multilayer
47	o	Pre-exponential

48

49

50

51

52

53

54

55

56

57

58 **Introduction**

59 Chestnut (*Castanea sativa M.*) is an important product of the Mediterranean
60 countries. World production was approximately about 1,220,000 t in 2007 (FAO,
61 2009). It is a seasonal food harvested in autumn and winter, and in order to extend
62 its useful life it is necessary to produce derived products, such as flour or starch.
63 These can be used for making bread, biscuits, cookies, snacks, flakes and pasta.
64 The derived products of chestnut present two specific advantages: low cholesterol
65 and free gluten contents for which these products are suitable for
66 hypercholesterolemic and celiac people, respectively.

67 Studies on new natural starches are essential in order to determine their best
68 applications and improve their utilization. Many authors have studied the
69 development of new starches for food industry (Alexander, 1996; Demiate et al.,
70 2001), although the literature about the chestnut flour and starch is scarce.
71 Particularly, data about sorption isotherms were not found.

72 The composition of fresh chestnut on dry basis is approximately 4.7 % of
73 protein, 14.0 % of fibre, 55.1 % of starch, 19.0 % of sucrose, 4.1 % of lipids and
74 others 3.1 % (Mataix et al., 1998; FAO, 2009).

75 The shelf life of food materials is usually limited by microbial growth; hence
76 several preservation processes are aimed to achieve the stability by reduction of
77 the moisture content to levels below those required by the micro-organisms for
78 survival and reproduction (Aguilera & Stanley, 1999). The preservation of foods
79 with high starch content depends essentially on its sorption parameters. For
80 example, some researchers considered that the sorption process occurs mainly on
81 the surface of starch grains (Ando et al., 2002), while others assume that the
82 sorption takes place inside the grains (Rebar et al., 1984).

83 Scott (1957) identified the equilibrium relative humidity of the environment
84 with the water activity (a_w) of the sample. Water activity is defined as the ratio
85 between vapour pressure of water in the food and vapour pressure of pure water at
86 the same temperature. The water activity is one of the main control variables in
87 food preservation technology. In this way, microbial growth, browning, lipid
88 oxidation, etc., and other physical properties such as colour, texture and density
89 are dependent on the water activity of the product (Yanniotis et al., 1989).
90 Moisture content and water activity data of foodstuffs are essential for the design
91 and optimization of many processes in food industry such as drying, packaging
92 and storage (Fortes & Okos, 1980). The relationship between the water activity
93 and the equilibrium moisture content (X) of the food samples at constant
94 temperature and pressure comes given by the water sorption isotherm. The
95 isotherm curves can be obtained in terms of adsorption or desorption, which are
96 not fully reversible. Therefore a distinction can be made between the isotherms
97 depending if the moisture levels within the products are increasing or decreasing
98 (Al-Muhtaseb et al, 2004a). Food systems typically exhibit Type II and III
99 (according to the BET classification, Brunauer et al., 1940) isotherms.

100 Water sorption isotherm equations are useful for predicting water sorption
101 properties of foods, although they provide little insight into the interaction of
102 water and food components (Leung, 1983). In the literature there are a number of
103 available models that describe sorption isotherms. These models can be divided
104 into several categories: kinetic models based on an absorbed mono-layer of water,
105 kinetic models based on a multi-layer and condensed film, semi-empirical models
106 and purely empirical models. The well-known (two parameters) BET model
107 (Brunauer et al., 1938) is the basis of some useful models to describe the

108 adsorption processes. In this way, the modified BET model (Brunauer et al., 1938)
109 and the Guggenheim-Anderson-de Boer (GAB) model (Van den Berg et al., 1981)
110 are three parameters models by considering of a limited number of adsorbed
111 layers or by assuming different heats of adsorption than heat of vapour
112 condensation, respectively. GAB model is recognised as the fundamental equation
113 for the characterisation of water sorption of food materials.

114 The effect of temperature on the sorption isotherm is of great importance since
115 food materials are exposed to a range of temperatures during storage and
116 processing, and the water activity changes with temperature.

117 The models can also be employed for evaluating some thermodynamic
118 properties. The total heat of sorption is the total energy required to transfer water
119 molecules from vapour state to a solid surface or vice-versa. It is useful, for
120 example, in predictive drying models as well as in the design of drying equipment
121 (Fasina, 2006).

122 The main aims of this work are: (i) to obtain experimental sorption isotherms
123 for chestnut (*Castanea sativa*, M.) flour and for chestnut and potato (*Solanum*
124 *tuberosum*, L.) starches at different temperatures; (ii) to fit the sorption data using
125 modified BET and GAB models; (iii) to determine the sorption heats; (iv) to
126 compare sorption isotherms obtained experimentally. Potato starch sorption
127 isotherms were previously reported by McMinn & Magee (2003), Al-Muhtaseb et
128 al. (2004a), Al-Muhtaseb et al. (2004b), McMinn et al. (2004) and McMinn et al.
129 (2005) in a more restricted temperatures range of 30 °C to 60 °C.

130

131

132

133 **Materials and Methods**

134 Raw Materials

135 Samples of chestnut (*Castanea sativa* Mill.) were obtained from a local
136 supermarket and selected with a uniform size and ripeness. Chestnuts were stored
137 at 4 °C until use. The average initial moisture content was 47.6% (wet basis).

138 Chestnuts were peeled, fragmented into small pieces and milled in a stainless
139 steel grinder (Taurus) with granulometric size above 500 µm. The resulting
140 chestnut flour was used to determine its sorption isotherms.

141 Chestnut starch was obtained using a representative portion of chestnut flour
142 (200 g). The chestnut flour was mixed with 400 mL of distilled water (ratio 1:2).
143 The mixture was filtered and separated into residue and filtrate. The residue was
144 mixed again with water in the same ratio (1:2) and re-filtered. The second filtrate
145 was added to the first filtrate and allowed to settle over 24 h. Settled solids were
146 separated from the supernatant and washed several times with distilled water
147 using a vacuum system, until a clear wash and white starch were obtained. The
148 resulting starch was dried in a vacuum oven at 50°C. The starch dry basis content
149 in the chestnut flour was 53.5 ± 1.3 %. A simple and rapid colorimeter method
150 was used in order to determine the amylose and amylopectine contents (Scott et
151 al., 1998). Obtained chestnut starch showed amylose content of 20.5 ± 0.6 % and
152 amylopectine content of 79.5 ± 0.6 %. Granulometric size of the obtained starch
153 was less 80 µm.

154 Potato starch was also extracted using the same method as for chestnut starch,
155 obtaining the same size and white colour. Starch content of potato was 75.2 ± 1.8
156 % (dry basis), and the amylose and amylopectine contents were 22.3 ± 0.4 % and
157 77.7 ± 0.4 %, respectively.

158 Equilibrium Data Determination

159 A static gravimetric technique was used to determine the equilibrium moisture
160 content of chestnut flour as well as chestnut and potato starches. This technique is
161 based on the use of saturated salt solutions in order to obtain constant water
162 activity values. The salt solutions were chosen to cover a wide range of water
163 activity from 0.093 to 0.909 at 20 °C. The chosen salt solutions (KOH, LiCl,
164 MgCl₂, K₂CO₃, Mg(NO₃)₂, NH₄NO₃, NaCl, KCl and BaCl₂) were prepared as
165 recommended by Greenspan (1977). Triplicate samples of, approximately, 0.2 g
166 were introduced in small glass containers which were placed above Petri dishes
167 inside the jars at constant water activity environment. In order to inhibit microbial
168 growth at water activity above 0.6 a small quantity of crystalline thymol was
169 placed inside the jars. The experiments were carried out at different temperatures
170 (20, 35, 50 and 65 °C).

171 The samples were periodically weighed using an analytical balance (Denver
172 Instrument SI-234) till a constant weight was reached (± 0.0004 g). The
173 equilibrium period was 6 to 8 weeks. Water activity of random samples after
174 achieving constant weight was measured in a Novasina Thermoconstanter TH2
175 hygrometer in order to check possible contaminations of the saturated salts
176 solutions. Finally, the moisture content (dry basis) of each sample was determined
177 by drying in a vacuum oven (Heraeus Vacutherm VT 6025) during at least 12 h at
178 70°C and 13.3 kPa (AOAC, 1995).

179

180 Sorption Isotherm Models

181 Modified BET model is a three parameter model that is given by the equation:

182

183
$$X = \frac{X_{MB} C_B a_w}{(1 - a_w)} \frac{1 - (N+1) a_w^N + N a_w^{N+1}}{1 + (C_B - 1) a_w - C_B a_w^{N+1}} \quad (1)$$

184 where X_{MB} represents moisture content of the monolayer, C_B is related to the
 185 difference between the chemical potential of the sorbate molecules in pure liquid
 186 state and in the first layer, and N is the number of the layers. This model can be
 187 applied in a broader range of water activity values than BET model that is usually
 188 restricted to be employed at $a_w < 0.4$ (Timmermann et al., 2001).

189 The Guggenheim-Anderson-de Boer (GAB) model (Van den Berg et al., 1981)
 190 was used in this work to describe the relationship between equilibrium moisture
 191 content and water activity at each temperature in the full range of water activity:

192
$$X = \frac{X_M C K a_w}{[(1 - K a_w)(1 - K a_w + C K a_w)]} \quad (2)$$

193 where X_M represents moisture content of the monolayer, C is related to sorption
 194 heat of the first layer and K is related to the heat of sorption of the multilayer.
 195 These parameters depend on temperature and characteristics of the product (Kim
 196 & Bhowmik, 1994):

197
$$X_M = X_{M0} \exp(H/RT) \quad (3)$$

198
$$C = C_0 \exp[(h_M - h_N)/RT] \quad (4)$$

199
$$K = K_0 \exp[(h_L - h_N)/RT] \quad (5)$$

200 where h_L is the heat of condensation of water vapour. According to Weast (1982),
 201 between 20 and 65°C the heat of condensation is a function of the temperature,
 202 and a linear relationship ($R^2 = 0.997$) can be established:

203
$$h_L = 45.04 - 0.0438T \quad (6)$$

204 $h_M - h_N$ and $h_L - h_N$ show strength of the bounding between water molecules in the
 205 respective layers. Particularly, $h_M - h_N$ represents the difference between monolayer

206 and multilayer sorption enthalpy, and h_L-h_N is the difference between the
207 condensation heat of water and the multilayer sorption heat.

208 The fitting parameters involved in both models were estimated using non-linear
209 multiparameter regression procedure with Table Curve software (Jandel
210 Scientific®). The goodness of the fittings was tested by calculating statistical
211 parameters such as coefficient of determination (R^2), mean relative percentage
212 deviation modulus (E) and root mean square error (E_{RMS}):

$$213 \quad E = \frac{100}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{|X_{\text{exp}} - X_{\text{cal}}|}{X_{\text{exp}}} \quad (7)$$

$$214 \quad E_{\text{RMS}} = \left[\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (X_{\text{exp}} - X_{\text{cal}})^2 \right]^{1/2} \quad (8)$$

215

216 Determination of Net Isothermic Heat of Sorption

217 The net isosteric sorption heat (h_e) provides the additional energy in order to
218 achieve food dehydration and it is defined as the difference between total isosteric
219 sorption heat and condensation heat. The net isosteric sorption heat was calculated
220 from the moisture sorption isotherms by Clausius-Clapeyron equation.

$$221 \quad \ln \left(\frac{a_{w2}}{a_{w1}} \right)_{X=\text{cte}} = \frac{h_e}{R} \left(\frac{1}{T_2} - \frac{1}{T_1} \right) \quad (9)$$

222 The net isosteric heats of sorption were evaluated at constant moisture contents.

223 Water activity values (a_{w2} and a_{w1}) were calculated using GAB model at each
224 moisture content and temperature tested.

225

226

227 **Results and Discussion**

228 Experimental Desorption Isotherms

229 The water desorption data of chestnut flour as well as chestnut and potato starches
230 at studied temperatures (20, 35, 50 and 65 °C) are shown in the Figs. 1, 2 and 3,
231 respectively. Each point is the average of three experimental determinations.
232 Moisture content increased when water activity increased in all systems studied. A
233 more detailed data analysis led to the identification two different regions in the
234 isotherm. At low and intermediate water activities, the so-called multilayer
235 sorption region, moisture content increased linearly with water activity; whereas
236 at high water activity levels, the so-called capillary condensation region, water
237 content increased no-linearly with water activity. This behaviour is more clear in
238 the sorption isotherms of potato starch at all temperatures and for chestnut flour at
239 temperature above 20°C. The determined isotherms were of type II according to
240 Brunauer's (Brunauer, 1940) classification.

241 Desorption isotherms were significantly influenced by the temperature. This
242 effect in the studied range of temperature can be described in two parts. At water
243 activities values less 0.65, the equilibrium moisture content of all studied systems
244 decreased when temperature increased. At water activities values above 0.65 a
245 different behaviour was observed between the flour and the starches. The obtained
246 sorption isotherms of chestnut and potato starches showed the same
247 aforementioned behaviour for water activity values below 0.65. The obtained
248 sorption isotherms of chestnut flour crossed over at this water activity value.
249 Vázquez et al. (2001) showed that desorption isotherms of chestnut fruit crossed
250 over at water activity above 0.6 and it was justified by the presence of secreted
251 sugar at their surface at high temperatures.

252 The main component of chestnut flour is starch, which comprises crystalline
253 and amorphous regions. The starch sorption isotherms are attributable to

254 hydrogen-bonding of water molecules to the available hydroxyl groups of the
255 substrate (Urquhart, 1959). The crystalline regions typically exhibit resistance to
256 solvent penetration. Hence, water effect is very small and the mobility of the
257 amorphous regions is restricted. However, as the water activity increases, the
258 sorbed water causes a subsequent swelling of the biopolymer, the degree of
259 crystallinity decreases and there is an increase of availability of the polar groups
260 to water molecules and, finally, the swelled polysaccharide forms a solution (Al-
261 Muhtaseb et al., 2004a).

262 Figs. 1 and 2 show that chestnut flour is a less hygroscopic material than
263 chestnut starch in a wide range of water activities. This behaviour was found at
264 water activity values above 0.12 at 20 °C and 0.17 at 35 °C. At 50 °C this
265 behaviour can be observed between water activity values of 0.11 and 0.83. At 65
266 °C both isotherms were practically the same until water activity value of 0.7 and
267 above this value, chestnut starch is less hygroscopic. The difference between
268 desorption isotherms of the two materials decreased when temperature increased.

269 Comparing Figs. 2 and 3 it can be observed that the equilibrium moisture
270 content values at 20, 35 and 50 °C for chestnut and potato starches were very
271 similar in the studied water activity range. The percentage deviations of moisture
272 contents in the range of 20 to 50°C were lower than 13%. At 65 °C the difference
273 between sorption isotherms of potato and chestnut starches increased, which can
274 be due to the gelatinization process of potato starch. Potato starch gelatinization
275 temperature is between 60 °C and 70 °C (Douzas et al., 1996) whereas chestnut
276 starch gelatinization temperature is above 65 °C (approximately 69.5 °C) (Demiate
277 et al., 2001). The obtained sorption isotherm for potato starch at 65 °C was very
278 similar to the obtained data for gel potato starch at 60 °C by McMinn et al. (2005).

279 The values of experimental data of this work agree with the reported values in
280 the literature by Aboubakar et al. (2008) for taro flour and starch and by Durakova
281 & Menkov (2004) for rice flour.

282

283 Fitting sorption models to experimental data

284 The modified BET model parameters (X_{MB} , C_B , and N) and GAB model
285 parameters (X_M , K , and C), Eqs. 1 and 2, at studied temperatures and the statistical
286 parameters (R^2 , E and E_{RMS}) are listed in Table 1 and 2, respectively. BET
287 parameters decreased (X_{MB} and N varied in a restricted range) following
288 Arrhenius' relationships with the increase of temperature. It is necessary to
289 indicate that modified BET model gave satisfactory fittings below 0.7 of water
290 activity for chestnut flour and below 0.8 for chestnut and potato starches. This fact
291 is because to the divergence of the function $1/(1 - a_w)$ (Eq. 1) when water activity
292 towards 1. GAB model could be applied satisfactorily in all range of water
293 activity. Similar results were also found when both models were applied to water
294 sorption in different polymers (Jonquieres and Fane, 1998) where it was
295 established that GAB model is valid in a broader range. By other hand,
296 Timmermann et al. (2001) established that monolayer moisture content is better
297 evaluated by GAB model because two parameters BET model underestimates its
298 value. In our case, X_{MB} (three parameters BET model) and X_M showed practically
299 the same values, indicating that both models can be considered as adequate to
300 evaluate the monolayer moisture content. In all cases, both models fitted
301 satisfactorily the experimental water desorption data because high coefficients of
302 determination ($R^2 > 0.974$ for modified BET model and $R^2 > 0.990$ for GAB
303 model), good standard error ($E < 6.5$ % for modified BET model and $E < 4.8$ %

304 for GAB model) and low root mean square error ($E_{RMS} < 0.0483$ for modified BET
305 model, and $E_{RMS} < 0.0290$ for potato starch) were obtained. Taking into account
306 reported results by Lomauro et al. (1985), a fit can be considered good when $E <$
307 10 %, thus the obtained results of this work can be considered validated.
308 Nevertheless, GAB model reported systematically better values of statistical
309 parameters and taking into account that is applicable satisfactorily in all the
310 experimental range it will be used in this work to analyze the obtained desorption
311 isotherms. GAB model fittings are shown in Figs. 1, 2 and 3 by lines.

312

313 Monolayer Moisture Content

314 The monolayer moisture content (X_M) is the minimum moisture content covering
315 hydrophilic sites on the material surface, and it is a necessary data for achieving
316 storage with minimum quality loss for long time. Therefore, at a given
317 temperature, the safest water activity level is related to X_M . For all studied systems
318 the monolayer moisture content decreased when temperature increased. The
319 average monolayer moisture content (kg (kg d.b.)^{-1}) calculated by GAB model
320 was 0.059 ± 0.007 for chestnut flour, 0.103 ± 0.021 for chestnut starch and 0.060
321 ± 0.028 for potato starch.

322 The effect of temperature is introduced in the original GAB model of three
323 parameters by means of Eqs. 3, 4 and 5 so obtaining as six parameter model (X_{M0} ,
324 C_0 , K_0 , h_L , h_M and h_N). These parameters are reported in Table 3. The presented
325 values in Table 3 were in the range of the obtained values by Al-Muhtaseb et al.
326 (2004a) for desorption isotherms of potato starch with high amylopectin content
327 ($C_0 = 0.003$ and $K_0 = 0.723$).

328

329 Modelling with Temperature: Net Isotheric Heat of Sorption

330 The obtained (h_M-h_N) values were positive as was expected, due to the strong
331 exothermic interaction of water vapour with primary sorption sites of the material.
332 The (h_L-h_N) values were smaller than (h_M-h_N) values. These values were in the
333 range of data reported by Al-Muhtaseb et al. (2004a) for desorption isotherms of
334 potato starch with high amylopectin content ($(h_M-h_N) = 21.5 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$ and $(h_L-h_N) =$
335 $0.567 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$). The sign of (h_L-h_N) was negative for chestnut flour which agree
336 with the reported data for chestnut by Vázquez et al. (2001) ($-218.9 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$).

337 The net isosteric heat of sorption (h_e) was determined by means of Clausius-
338 Clapeyron equation (Eq. 9). The mean net isosteric heat values for chestnut flour
339 and potato starch are shown in Fig 4 in terms of moisture content at 35 °C. The
340 calculated net isosteric heat values for chestnut starch are presented in the Fig. 4
341 (where the temperatures indicated are the average temperatures used to calculate
342 h_e with Eq. 9). For chestnut starch, more detailed study is shown because it is one
343 of the main aims of this work. As it can be seen in the Fig. 4, h_e values slightly
344 decreased with temperature at the same moisture content.

345 The net heat of sorption decreased with the increase in moisture content. At
346 lower moisture content chestnut flour and potato starch presented higher values of
347 h_e than chestnut starch. These higher values of h_e at low moisture contents can be
348 explained because the water molecules are tightly bounded to the food
349 components in what is called a monolayer, and therefore the amount of energy
350 required to remove these water molecules is very high. In the case of chestnut
351 starch the monolayer moisture contents estimated by GAB model are the highest
352 of the studied systems and water is more weakly linked. At values above 0.15

353 $\text{kg}(\text{kg.d.b.})^{-1}$, h_e of chestnut flour was approximated to zero and the h_e values of
354 chestnut and potato starches were in the same range.

355

356 **Conclusions**

357 GAB model was more adequate than modified three parameters BET model to fit
358 experimental desorption isotherms because is applicable in experimental range of
359 water activities and reported better values of statistical parameters. The Clausius-
360 Clapeyron equation provides an acceptable exponential relationship between the
361 net isosteric sorption heat and equilibrium moisture content. At lower moisture
362 contents, chestnut flour and potato starch showed higher values of h_e as compared
363 to chestnut starch. Desorption isotherms for chestnut and potato starches are very
364 similar at 20, 35 and 50°C. The deviation from equilibrium moisture contents at
365 the same water activity among the isotherms at the same temperature was less
366 than 13 %. At 65°C the isotherms for both the starches were different because of
367 the gelatinization of potato starch. The main difference between the obtained
368 desorption isotherms for chestnut flour and those obtained for both starches was
369 the existence of intersection point at 0.65 of water activity. Desorption isotherms
370 for chestnut flour and starch showed that the chestnut flour was less hygroscopic
371 than chestnut starch in presence of other components. The difference between
372 desorption isotherms of both products decreased with the increase in temperature.

373

374 **Acknowledgements**

375 The authors acknowledge the financial support to Ministerio de Educación y
376 Ciencia of Spain and FEDER (CTQ 2007-62009/PPQ).

377 **References**

- 378 Aboubakar, Njintang YN, Scher J & Mbofung CMF (2008) Physicochemical,
379 thermal properties and microstructure of six varieties of taro (*Colocasia esculenta*
380 L. Schott) flours and starches. *Journal of Food Engineering*, 86, 294-305.
- 381 Aguilera JM & Stanley DW (1999) Microstructural principles of food processing
382 and engineering, pp 373–411. Aspen Publication, Maryland, USA.
- 383 Alexander RJ (1996) New starches for food application. *Cereal food world*, 41,
384 796-798.
- 385 Al-Muhtaseb AH, McMinn WAM & Magee TRA (2004a) Water sorption
386 isotherms of starch powders. Part 1: mathematical description of experimental
387 data. *Journal of Food Engineering*, 61, 297–307.
- 388 Al-Muhtaseb AH, McMinn WAM & Magee TRA (2004b) Water sorption
389 isotherms of starch powders. Part 2: Thermodynamic characteristics. *Journal of*
390 *Food Engineering*, 62, 135–142.
- 391 Ando H, Tang H, Watanabe K & Mitsunaga T (2002) Some Physicochemical
392 Properties of Large, Medium and Small Granule Starches in Fractions of Wheat
393 Grain. *Food Science and Technology Research*, 8, 24-27.
- 394 AOAC (1995) Official methods of analysis. Association of Official Analytical
395 Chemistry. Washington, USA.
- 396 Brunauer S, Deming LS, Deming WE & Teller E (1940) On a theory of the Van
397 der Waals adsorption of gases. *Journal of the American Chemical Society* 62,
398 1723–1732.
- 399 Brunauer, S, Emmet PH & Teller E (1938) Adsorption of gases in multimolecular
400 layers. *Journal of the American Chemical Society* 60, 309–319.

401 Demiate IM, Oetterer M & Wosiacki G (2001) Characterization of chestnut
402 (*Castanea sativa*, Mill) starch for industrial utilization. Brazilian archives of
403 biology and technology, 44 (1), 69-78.

404 Douzas JP, Marechal PA, Coquille JC & Gervais P (1996) Microscopic Study of
405 Starch Gelatinization under High Hydrostatic Pressure. Journal of Agriculture and
406 Food Chemistry, 44, 1403-1408.

407 Durakova AG & Menkov ND (2004) Moisture sorption characteristics of rice
408 flour. Nahrung/Food, 48, 137-140.

409 FAO. (2009). < http://www.fao.org/infoods/directory_en.stm >

410 Fasina OO (2006) Thermodynamic properties of sweet potato. Journal of Food
411 Engineering, 75, 149–155.

412 Fortes M & Okos MR (1980) Drying Theories: Their Bases and Limitations as
413 Applied to Food and Grains. In: A.S. Mujumdar (ed.) Advances in Drying, Vol 1,
414 pp 119–154. New York, USA.

415 Greenspan L (1977) Humidity fixed points of binary saturated aqueous solutions.
416 Journal of Research of the National Bureau of Standards Section A, 81, 89-102.

417 Jonquieres A & Fane A (1998) Modified BET models for modelling water vapour
418 sorption in hydrophilic glassy polymers and systems deviating strongly from
419 ideality. Journal of Applied Polymer Science, 67, 1415-1430.

420 Kim SS & Bhowmik SR (1994) Moisture sorption isotherms of concentrated
421 yogurt and microwave vacuum dried yogurt powder. Journal of Food Engineering,
422 21, 157–175.

423 Leung HK (1983) Water activity and other colligative properties of foods. In:
424 ASAE annual meeting, paper no. 83-6508. Chicago, USA.

425 Lomauro CJ, Bakshi AS & Labuza TP (1985) Evaluation of food moisture
426 sorption isotherm equations. Part I. Fruit, Vegetables and meat products,
427 *Lebensmittel Wissenschaft Technologie*, 18, 111-115.

428 Mataix J, Mañas M & Llopis J (1998). *Tabla de Composición de Alimentos*
429 *españoles*. University of Granada, Granada, Spain.

430 McMinn WAM & Magee TRA (2003) Thermodynamic properties of moisture
431 sorption of potato. *Journal of Food Engineering*, 60, 155–157.

432 McMinn WAM, Al-Muhtaseb AH & Magee TRA (2004) Moisture sorption
433 characteristics of starch gels. Part II: Thermodynamic properties. *Journal of Food*
434 *Process Engineering*, 27, 213–227.

435 McMinn WAM, Al-Muhtaseb AH & Magee TRA (2005) Enthalpy-entropy
436 compensation in sorption phenomena of starch materials. *Food research*
437 *international*, 38, 505–510.

438 Rebar V, Fischbach ER, Apostolopoulos D & Kokini JL (1984) Thermodynamics
439 of water and ethanol adsorption on four starches as model biomass separation
440 systems. *Biotechnology and bioengineering*, 26 (5), 513-517.

441 Scott JM, Hugh JC & Colin JR (1998) A simple and rapid colorimetric method for
442 the determination of amylose in starch products. *Starch*, 50, 158-163.

443 Scott WJ (1957) Water relations of foods spoilage microorganisms. *Advances in*
444 *Food Research*, 7, 83-127.

445 Timmermann EO, Chirife J & Iglesias HA (2001) Water sorption isotherms of
446 foods and foodstuffs: BET or GAB parameters? *Journal of Food Engineering*, 48,
447 19-31.

448 Urquhart AR (1959) Differential enthalpy of sorption in dried fruits. *Journal of*
449 *Food Engineering*, 14, 327-335.

450 Van den Berg C & Bruin S (1981) Water activity and its estimation in food
451 systems; Theoretical aspects. In: Water Activity: Influences on Food Quality, pp
452 1–61. Academic Press Inc., New York, USA.

453 Vázquez G, Chenlo F & Moreira R (2001) Modeling of desorption isotherms of
454 chestnut: Influence of temperature and evaluation of isosteric heats. *Drying*
455 *Technology*, 19 (6), 1189–1199.

456 Weast RC (1982) Handbook of chemistry and physics. CRC Press, Boca Raton,
457 FL.

458 Yanniotis S, Nikolettopoulos P & Pappas G (1989) Sorption models for dried
459 fruits. In: Proceedings of the 5th International Congress on Engineering and Food,
460 Karlsruhe, Germany.

461

462

463

464

465

466

467

468

469

470

471

472

473

474

475 **Captions for Figures**

476

477 **Fig. 1.** Experimental data for equilibrium moisture contents of chestnut flour.

478 Lines correspond to the GAB model (Eq. 2).

479

480 **Fig. 2.** Experimental data for equilibrium moisture contents of chestnut starch.

481 Lines correspond to the GAB model (Eq. 2).

482

483 **Fig. 3.** Experimental data for equilibrium moisture contents of potato starch. Lines

484 correspond to the GAB model (Eq. 2).

485

486 **Fig. 4.** Effect of moisture content on the net isosteric heat of sorption for chestnut

487 flour and starch, and potato starch.

488

489

490 **Fig. 1.** Experimental data for equilibrium moisture contents of chestnut flour.

491 Lines correspond to the GAB model (Eq. 2).

492

493 **Fig. 2.** Experimental data for equilibrium moisture contents of chestnut starch.

494 Lines correspond to the GAB model (Eq. 2).

495

496 **Fig. 3.** Experimental data for equilibrium moisture contents of potato starch. Lines

497 correspond to the GAB model (Eq. 2).

498

499 **Fig. 4.** Effect of moisture content on the net isosteric heat of sorption for chestnut

500 flour and starch, and potato starch.

501

502 **Table 1** Values for the parameters of modified BET model (Eq. 1) and statistical
 503 coefficients (R^2 , E and E_{RMS}) for sorption isotherms of chestnut flour, chestnut and
 504 potato starches at several temperatures.

Parameters	Chestnut flour ^a				Chestnut starch ^b				Potato starch ^b			
Temperature (°C)	20	35	50	65	20	35	50	65	20	35	50	65
X_{MB}	0.065	0.059	0.055	0.054	0.120	0.102	0.095	0.081	0.078	0.070	0.057	0.031
C_B	9.44	6.76	5.27	4.69	2.17	2.11	1.87	1.79	6.82	4.63	4.49	4.10
N	4.47	4.30	4.19	3.90	5.34	5.01	4.50	4.20	10.8	9.03	6.01	5.50
R^2	0.983	0.994	0.995	0.996	0.986	0.987	0.990	0.987	0.974	0.981	0.988	0.984
E	0.060	0.039	0.037	0.034	0.052	0.050	0.047	0.051	0.065	0.056	0.048	0.053
E_{RMS}	0.0452	0.0304	0.0291	0.0272	0.0354	0.0343	0.0310	0.0350	0.0581	0.0483	0.0300	0.0389

505 a. Fitting in the range of $0 < a_w < 0.7$.

506 b. Fitting in the range of $0 < a_w < 0.8$.

507

508

509

510

511 **Table 2** Values for the parameters of GAB model (Eq. 2) and statistical
 512 coefficients (R^2 , E and E_{RMS}) for sorption isotherms of chestnut flour, chestnut and
 513 potato starches at several temperatures.

Parameters	Chestnut flour				Chestnut starch				Potato starch			
Temperature (°C)	20	35	50	65	20	35	50	65	20	35	50	65
X_M	0.066	0.059	0.056	0.055	0.124	0.109	0.097	0.082	0.079	0.071	0.057	0.032
K	0.759	0.863	0.909	0.928	0.744	0.743	0.742	0.741	0.892	0.864	0.863	0.863
C	16.5	9.48	4.91	4.02	4.96	4.11	3.51	3.24	15.87	10.15	8.46	4.45
R^2	0.998	0.999	0.999	0.996	0.999	0.996	0.998	0.997	0.997	0.997	0.990	0.990
E	0.040	0.039	0.038	0.044	0.041	0.044	0.043	0.043	0.045	0.044	0.048	0.047
E_{RMS}	0.0252	0.0245	0.0241	0.0270	0.0253	0.0273	0.0267	0.0271	0.0281	0.0283	0.0290	0.0289

514

515

516

517 **Table 3** Parameters for GAB model of the Eqs. (3), (4), and (5) in terms of
 518 temperature.

	C_0 (-)	K_0 (-)	X_{M0} (kg (kg d.b.) ⁻¹)	H (kJ mol ⁻¹)	(h_M-h_N) (kJ mol ⁻¹)	(h_L-h_N) (kJ mol ⁻¹)
Chestnut flour	$2.44 \cdot 10^{-4}$	3.48	$1.64 \cdot 10^{-2}$	3.33	27.0	-3.65
Chestnut starch	0.189	0.722	$5.97 \cdot 10^{-3}$	7.42	7.92	$7.38 \cdot 10^{-2}$
Potato starch	$2.11 \cdot 10^{-3}$	0.701	$1.34 \cdot 10^{-4}$	15.8	21.8	0.567

519